

STUDENT MOTIVATION AS A PEDAGOGICAL CONDITION FOR THE FORMATION OF DIGITAL COMPETENCE IN MASTER'S DEGREE PROGRAMMES

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Annotation. The article examines the problem of developing digital competence among future Master's in Tourism. It establishes the need to identify pedagogical conditions as a factor in ensuring the quality of the educational process. This study aims to provide a theoretical justification for encouraging students as a pedagogical condition for developing digital competence in master's degree programs. During the study, a set of general scientific theoretical methods was employed, including analysis, synthesis, systematization, and generalization of data from scientific, methodological, and specialized literature. The first pedagogical condition for the formation of digital competence of future Master's in Tourism is determined to be the encouragement of students to form digital competence in the context of master's training. The essence of this condition lies in creating positive, purposeful motivation and the need to acquire the appropriate level of digital competence for future Master's in Tourism. It has been found that the effective implementation of pedagogical conditions requires the organization, form, and content of this process to be streamlined. The structuring of the first pedagogical condition for the formation of digital competence of future Master's in Tourism is presented as a holistic system of organic synthesis of content-information (goals, objectives, content essence, tasks, and expected results) and procedural-methodological (generalization of the system of actions and methods of practical implementation of pedagogical conditions) elements. The provisions of scientific and methodological support for a specific pedagogical condition are substantiated on the basis of the implementation of personality-oriented, activity-based, and competence-based approaches in the formation of digital competence of future Master's in Tourism. The expected result of the implementation of the substantiated pedagogical condition of encouraging students to develop digital competence in the context of master's training is seen in the achievement of high levels of value-motivational criteria in the development of the axiological component of digital competence of future Master's in Tourism.

Keywords: digital competence, tourism, master's degree, component, motivation.

Заохочення студентів як педагогічна умова формування цифрової компетентності в умовах магістерської підготовки

Анотація. У статті досліджено проблему формування цифрової компетентності майбутніх магістрів у сфері туризму. Установлена потреба виокремлення педагогічних

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умов, як чинника забезпечення якості освітнього процесу. Метою даного дослідження є теоретичне обґрунтування заохочення студентів як педагогічної умови формування цифрової компетентності в умовах магістерської підготовки. У процесі дослідження використано комплекс загальнонаукових теоретичних методів: аналіз, синтез, систематизація, узагальнення даних науково-методичної та спеціальної літератури. Першою педагогічною умовою формування цифрової компетентності майбутніх магістрів у сфері туризму визначено заохочення студентів до формування цифрової компетентності в умовах магістерської підготовки. Сутність цієї умови полягає у створенні позитивної цілеспрямованої мотивації та потреби у набутті належного рівня цифрової компетентності майбутніх магістрів у сфері туризму. Досліджено, що ефективне упровадження педагогічних умов вимагає упорядкування організації, форми і змісту цього процесу. Представлено структурування першої педагогічної умови формування цифрової компетентності майбутніх магістрів у сфері туризму у якості у якості цілісної системи органічного синтезу змістовно-інформаційного (цілі, мети, змістовної сутності, завдань та очікуваного результату) та процесуально-методичного (узагальнення системи дій та методики практичної реалізації педагогічних умов) елементів. Обґрунтовано положення науково-методичного супроводу визначеної педагогічної умови на основі упровадження особистісно-орієнтованого, діяльнісного та компетентнісного підходів у ході формування цифрової компетентності майбутніх магістрів у сфері туризму. Очікуваний результат реалізації обґрунтованої педагогічної умови заохочення студентів до формування цифрової компетентності в умовах магістерської підготовки вбачаємо у досягненні показників високого рівня ціннісно-мотиваційного критерію у розвитку аксіологічного компоненту цифрової компетентності майбутніх магістрів у сфері туризму.

Ключові слова: цифрова компетентність, туризм, магістр, заохочення, мотивація.

Introduction

The development of the tourism industry correlates with the needs and trends of the global market, increasing the competitiveness of the domestic tourism industry, which continues to recover strongly after the pandemic. Achieving the set goals, taking into account the specifics of national development, requires the availability of highly qualified professional human capital [1]. In this context, in addition to investments in infrastructure and equipment, there is a need to understand the implications of current and future changes in skills and to make appropriate investments in the training of future masters in tourism, in particular, to overcome the consequences of rapid technological change.

Due to the dynamic technological changes taking place in the sector, understanding and quickly assessing the needs of the tourism industry is defined [10] as a fundamental principle in the training of employees who are fully proficient in modern practical knowledge, innovative tools, and sustainable strategies for the development of the tourism industry. Given that technology as a term implies the practical application of knowledge to create something completely new, its development enables and constantly creates new types of activities [6]. Therefore, radical changes in the field of tourism are currently impossible without the context of employees mastering digital competence.

Addressing the issue of effectively developing the digital competence of tourism education seekers has become an urgent imperative. Of exceptional importance is the creation of a qualitatively new system for organizing master's degree programs that will provide future Master's in Tourism with opportunities to master digital competence that meets the modern challenges of professional activity and trends in the development of the tourism industry. Therefore, it is necessary to resolve problematic issues in the direction of eliminating contradictions in the formation of digital competence of future Master's in Tourism and modern challenges in meeting the needs of the tourism sector for highly qualified employees.

The issue of professional training of specialists in the field of tourism and the formation of appropriate competencies has been widely discussed in contemporary scientific works [3, 6, 10, 13]. Experts agree that the current development of tourism education is based on the intensive use of innovations [1, 12, 16, 18].

According to certain conclusions [3, 7] of specific studies, the modern progress of professional training of specialists to ensure the effective formation of competencies requires the fulfillment of a specific list of pedagogical conditions. It is these conditions that are recognized [8, 18] as a powerful lever in resolving certain pedagogical contradictions that are an obstacle to the acquisition of a high level of competencies.

Pedagogical conditions as correlates of the effectiveness of the pedagogical process are considered in a number of scientific works [3, 17, 18]. However, it has been proven [9] that pedagogical conditions should be considered exclusively in the context of specific issues. In the future, we intend to take as a basis the conclusions of Lytvyn, who states that "the ambiguity of the scientific and pedagogical term 'condition' is related to the different lexical meanings of the commonly used word 'condition': it is that on which the result depends; the requirements that one party imposes on another; an agreement between parties; a rule accepted in a particular field" [8, p. 11].

Based on the generalization of the main positions presented regarding the need to identify pedagogical conditions as a factor in ensuring the quality of the pedagogical process, we consider it appropriate to clarify the substantive essence of the pedagogical conditions for the formation of digital competence of future Master's in Tourism.

The formulation of article purpose. The purpose of this study is to provide a theoretical justification for encouraging students as a pedagogical condition for the formation of digital competence in the context of master's training.

Results

In order to conduct scientific research in a specific direction, let us clarify the understanding of the essence of pedagogical conditions for the formation of digital competence of future Master's in Tourism. Therefore, we present our vision of the pedagogical conditions for the formation of digital competence of future Master's in Tourism as a synthesized use of the potential of all possible resources of the educational process, such as forms, methods, and means, to create opportunities, circumstances, beliefs, and factors of purposeful influence on the development of the axiological, gnoseological, and activity components of digital competence, which ensure the individual educational trajectory of Master's in Tourism in achieving indicators corresponding to a high (creative) level of their digital competence.

We are convinced that it is precisely the awareness of this position that is necessary for the effective integration of pedagogical conditions into the practice of the educational process of future Master's in Tourism. Their practical implementation requires a combination of effective pedagogical strategies and the use of innovative technologies for the formation of digital competence of future Master's in Tourism, which is decisive in ensuring the effectiveness of this process. At the same time, we agree with Fedorchenko, who states that "the most difficult problem is the selection and structuring of the content of educational material by the criteria of scientificity, systematicity, and necessity" [3, p. 313].

In the future, in our research, we will use the thesis of Lytvyn, according to which "it is advisable to formulate pedagogical conditions in the form of rules for their implementation, which provide for the purposeful execution of certain procedures: development, provision, support, maintenance, etc." [8, p. 56]. This vision is based on a systematic approach, which ensures the formation of a system of pedagogical conditions that provides for their comprehensive systematic implementation in practice. According to Medynska, the "systematic approach provides a structured basis for planning, implementing, and evaluating the educational process" [11, p. 140].

However, when developing a systematic vision of the pedagogical conditions for the formation of digital competence in future Master's in Tourism, we anticipate the possibility of making adjustments in the course of solving the tasks of the educational process. Therefore, presenting our approach in substantiating the provisions of scientific and methodological support for a specific pedagogical condition, we organize it in such a way that its practical implementation ensures positive dynamics in the levels of digital competence of future Master's in Tourism.

Based on the results of our research, the first pedagogical condition for the formation of digital competence among future Master's in Tourism is to encourage students to develop digital competence in the context of master's training. In our understanding, the essence of this condition lies in creating positive, purposeful motivation and the need to acquire the appropriate level of digital competence for future Master's in Tourism.

First, let us return to digital competence, which is recognized [5] as a factor in the success of professional training. Undoubtedly, digital competence in the field of tourism has now gone beyond the simple development of technical skills necessary for the performance of professional duties [12]. In this regard, the conclusions [14, 15] are significant, proving the need for a strategy to correlate the development of digital competence with the narratives of modern social development.

Therefore, at the heart of the first pedagogical condition for the formation of digital competence in future Master's in Tourism is the need to create an understanding that digital competence is not only a key factor in ensuring employment and other aspects of professional realization in the field of tourism, but also a modern means of exchanging information in any sphere of public life [13].

In our study, we consider it necessary to use the conclusions of researchers [3, 7, 9], who consider encouragement to be a means of pedagogical influence that should be used to stimulate motivation in a particular type of activity. Since the issue of encouragement in the formation of professional competencies of future Master's in Tourism has not been studied in the existing scientific literature, we focus our research attention on the following, using the findings of researchers from various fields of knowledge.

Motivation is at the heart of encouragement. As a process that initiates, directs, and supports purposeful behavior [17], we consider knowledge about motivating factors to be a basic factor in persistent and purposeful actions in the formation of digital competence of future Master's in Tourism. Therefore, there is no doubt that the problem of acquiring high-quality digital competence must first be actualized, that is, made individually meaningful for each future master's student.

When arguing for ways to build motivation, let's pay attention to the constantly increasing requirements for digital competence among Master's in Tourism. It's totally natural that this is a result of introducing the latest information and communication technologies, which are driving revolutionary changes in tourism. In particular, it is worth paying attention to the emergence of new professions in tourism that require knowledge of artificial intelligence, data analytics, virtual reality, robotics, etc. Despite this, digitalization is not exclusively a factor in the creation of new knowledge and activities that are dynamically changing the field of tourism; they obviously need to be synthesized with existing ones.

It is also worth considering that personal orientation is considered to be the leading factor in the development of education. We are convinced that such orientation is a key factor and a prerequisite for the formation of motivation in the course of professional training.

Undoubtedly, effective learning is based on a personal desire for self-improvement. Accordingly, success in a particular type of activity can be achieved through continuous learning. This is in line with Maslow's classification of needs [17]. According to this, at the top of the pyramid are self-actualization and the desire for self-improvement.

These facts convince us that encouraging the development of digital competence should integrate existing knowledge, take into account the dynamic development of digital technologies, awareness of the importance of mastering new digital solutions for professional growth in the field of tourism, and personal motivational factors. We understand that the implementation of such a position is based on a synthesis of holistic, competency-based, activity-based, and personality-oriented approaches.

In this regard, we propose creating incentives and an appropriate level of motivation for the formation of digital competence in master's degree programs, in particular by promoting self-education among future masters in the field of information and communication technologies. The latter is now recognized as a social need for professional training [16]. It is becoming particularly important given that modern professional growth in the field of tourism lies in the range of cooperation and competition. We are confident that a high and quality level of digital competence is a powerful lever for future masters to avoid risks in their professional activities.

There is reason to believe that the scientific, methodological, and didactic content of the educational component, which should ensure the implementation of incentives for the formation of digital competence, can be realized by creating digital educational media based on the use of social networking sites for the exchange of relevant information in the field of tourism in real time.

In response to the challenges of the digital society, given that information and communication technologies have no national borders, we consider it necessary to strengthen the internationalization of educational resources and programs in the field of tourism. In our opinion, it is worth using podcasts on specific topics, in particular in independent work, online materials, and also creating your own. There is no doubt that the use of these tools encourages future masters to engage in self-development and exchange ideas.

The development of critical thinking skills as a basis for motivation requires the development of self-assessment models [2]. The task of such a model is to identify existing problems and prospects for their elimination. We consider it appropriate to create a questionnaire that will serve to stimulate reflection on the identified problems, opportunities, and the importance of an adequate level of digital competence for professional growth in the field of tourism.

A properly designed and correctly applied self-assessment model contributes not only to increasing the incentive to develop digital competence, but also to the quality of this process and adaptation to new challenges. We must emphasize that it is important in such a model to outline the benchmark of one's own expectations. Rewards for each achievement will subconsciously motivate future masters to continuous development [16].

The next element used in the implementation of the first pedagogical condition is the development of a practical course that can be used to implement an active learning model. In making this choice, we were guided by the so-called "learning pyramid," according to which 50% of the material is learned in discussion groups. In such a course, future masters will have the opportunity to present their vision for the development and improvement of digital competence in the field of tourism, work on various innovative start-up projects, and seek solutions to problems in this area. The feasibility of this choice in the development of encouraging the formation of digital competence of future masters is based on the opportunities of the workshop course in the development of critical thinking, self-reflection, personal interaction in the process of professional activity in the field of tourism, creativity, and analytical thinking [4]. At the same time, we ensure the development of cognitive activity and motivation for self-improvement.

We envision the workshop course for the formation of digital competence of future Master's in Tourism as a creative, interactive research practice of formulating ideas, experimenting, and receiving feedback. In this sense, involvement in the process of acquiring

digital competence and the organic development of ideas encourage future masters to become active participants in the process, focused on the qualitative formation of their digital competence, encouraging them to search for solutions.

Ensuring the effective implementation of pedagogical conditions requires streamlining the organization, form, and content of this process. In the most general form, we present the algorithm for the implementation of pedagogical conditions as a holistic system of organic synthesis of content-informational and procedural-methodological elements. We consider such structuring as a means of integrating the content resource of the presented pedagogical conditions in order to achieve the effectiveness of the proposed innovations.

The content and information element in our algorithm is a generalization of the goal, purpose, substantive essence, tasks, and expected result. The procedural and methodological element, as we understand it, involves a substantive generalization of the system of actions aimed at implementing the positions of the content and information element. We present it as an algorithmic, scientific and methodological support for the practical implementation of pedagogical conditions. Therefore, this element provides for a sequence of implementation procedures, methods, tools (means), and the establishment of actions. In general, this involves the availability of information support based on the use of modern technologies and methods.

The structure of the first pedagogical condition for the formation of digital competence of future Master's in Tourism – encouraging students to form digital competence in the conditions of master's training – is presented as follows.

The goal is to ensure the effectiveness of the educational and pedagogical process of master's training based on the implementation of the axiological component of the formation of digital competence of future Master's in Tourism.

The objective is to implement high-level value-motivational criteria in the development of the axiological component of the formation of digital competence of future Master's in Tourism.

The substantive essence is knowledge and understanding of digital competence as a competitive advantage in the field of tourism and the basis for professional establishment; knowledge of how digital technologies can support personal interaction in the process of professional activity in the field of tourism, creativity, and analytical thinking; awareness of information and communication technologies as a catalyst for innovation in professional activities in the field of tourism.

Tasks – creating sustainable motivation for the formation of digital competence in the context of master's training by stimulating self-development and continuous professional improvement of future Master's in Tourism; awareness by future masters of the need to master the skills of working with information and communication technologies in the field of tourism; to develop critical and analytical thinking, creative problem-solving skills in the field of digital competence; to develop the need for independent self-improvement of digital competence and self-reflection; to develop sustainable motivation to master modern information and communication technologies at a high professional level for professional improvement; developing an understanding of the interdependence of digital skills, knowledge, and abilities and interaction in professional activities in the field of tourism and interaction with other team members; gaining awareness of the importance of digital skills as critical for both personal and professional growth in the field of tourism.

The expected result is the achievement of high levels of value-motivational criteria in the development of the axiological component of digital competence of future Master's in Tourism.

The procedural and methodological element of the implementation of the first pedagogical condition – encouraging students to develop digital competence in the context of master's training according to our design – involves the use of discussion, project, and facilitation technologies.

The means of implementing discussion and project technologies are the case method and the project method. The expediency of using these means lies in the possibility of taking into account the personal opinions of future masters in an optimal format and reaching agreement in the process of active interaction, which contributes to the development of the need for self-improvement.

In general, the use of the selected means is based on an interdisciplinary approach, which is currently becoming the leading approach in education and is based on taking into account the different opinions of future professionals, their active participation, and interaction to achieve the effective implementation of the tasks of the first pedagogical condition.

The facilitation technology, which we consider appropriate to use in the implementation of the first pedagogical condition, arose against the backdrop of the fact that digital skills, which are integral parts of the transition of the education system to overcome the challenges of the 21st century, are now unquestionably recognized as the main driving force for rethinking educational technologies. We believe it is necessary to focus on the potential for self-development and interaction of future masters in the process of forming digital competence in the application of facilitation technology. In this way, we create a desire for self-development and self-improvement in future masters and stimulate positive dynamics of personal development.

Facilitation in pedagogy involves drawing on the personal experience of each participant in the educational process, followed by mutual enrichment of the experience of participation in the group, with support for activity and a mandatory combination of practice [16]. Therefore, despite the fact that scientific sources have not yet found proposals for the implementation of this technology in the development of digital competence, we have implemented our position on its use in the implementation of the first pedagogical condition.

With the active participation of future masters, we are introducing personality-oriented and competency-based approaches in the process of forming their digital competence. The organization and activation of discussion activities among future masters stimulate the process of acquiring new knowledge based on their research activities. The means used to implement this technology include the creation of virtual reality tours, training sessions, seminars, interactive modules, open discussions, etc.

Therefore, by focusing the educational process on self-development and personality-oriented development of future masters, we stimulate the development of motivation to achieve compliance of their digital training with the modern needs of the tourism sector, the appropriate level of their professional training, and the achievement of a synergistic effect. The quality of the implementation of the first pedagogical condition involves achieving the expected result, which embodies the formation of the axiological structural component of the digital competence of future Master's in Tourism.

Conclusions

The current progress in the professional training of specialists in the field of tourism to ensure the effective formation of digital competence requires the implementation of a specific list of pedagogical conditions. According to the results of the research, the first pedagogical condition for the formation of digital competence of future Master's in Tourism is to encourage students to form digital competence in the conditions of master's training. In our understanding, the essence of this condition lies in creating positive, purposeful motivation and the need to acquire the appropriate level of digital competence for future Master's in Tourism.

Encouraging the formation of digital competence should integrate existing knowledge, take into account the dynamic development of digital technologies, awareness of the importance of mastering new digital solutions for professional growth in the field of tourism, and personal motivational factors.

Ensuring the effective implementation of pedagogical conditions requires streamlining the organization, form, and content of this process. We present the algorithm for the implementation of pedagogical conditions as a holistic system of organic synthesis of content-informational (goals, objectives, content essence, tasks, and expected results) and procedural-methodological (generalization of the system of actions and methods of practical implementation of pedagogical conditions) elements.

The list of proposed means of encouraging students to develop digital competence in the context of master's degree training includes the following: digital educational media based on the use of social networking sites, the development of self-assessment models, the case method, and the project method.

The quality of the implementation of the first pedagogical condition involves achieving the expected result, which embodies the formation of the axiological structural component of the digital competence of future Master's in Tourism.

We see prospects for further research in the theoretical justification and identification of the second pedagogical condition for the formation of digital competence of future masters in tourism.

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